

GreenEURproject

Methodology

Quantitative metrics for environmental assessment

Authors:

Prof. Dr. Müfide Banar, Eskişehir Technical University

Prof. Dr. Aysun Özkan, Eskişehir Technical University

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Zerrin Günkaya, Eskişehir Technical University

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Alp Özdemir, Eskişehir Technical University

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Acronyms

FRSP	Fossil Resource Scarcity potential
GWP	Global Warming Potential
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MRSP	Mineral Resource Scarcity Potential
SODP	Stratospheric Ozone Depletion Potential
WC	Water Consumption

About the project

In recent years, the European Union has placed sustainable development at the forefront of its priorities, with ambitious goals to embed environmental responsibility across all initiatives. These objectives are deeply rooted in EU policies that increasingly aim to address the environmental impact of projects funded under Erasmus+ and beyond. While many EU-funded projects make significant contributions to education, research, and innovation, they also leave an ecological footprint—from travel and material use to energy consumption and waste. However, without a standardized framework for assessing these impacts, the environmental risks associated with such activities often remain unaddressed.

The GreenEURproject aims to change this by introducing a green label that evaluates the environmental impact of EU-funded projects. The initiative provides a pioneering approach to integrating sustainability into project planning and execution. The green label, complemented by practical tools such as a user-friendly impact calculator and detailed assessment guidelines, will empower project leaders to reduce ecological footprints from the very beginning. Through these resources, the GreenEURproject seeks to inspire and support project leaders, EU institutions, and evaluators in adopting eco-conscious practices, fostering a collective effort toward a greener future.

Key Outputs of the Project

- **Environmental Impact Calculator:** A quantitative tool designed to assess sustainability metrics, enabling stakeholders to identify and mitigate environmental risks effectively.
- **Green Label:** A clear and accessible certification awarded to projects based on their environmental performance, promoting transparency and encouraging best practices.
- **Guidelines and Handbook:** A comprehensive resource tailored for diverse stakeholders—including project leaders, EU institutions, and national agencies—offering actionable eco-friendly practices and key indicators for ranking projects.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Targeted proposals for EU policymakers to embed sustainability in project evaluation processes and promote eco-conscious practices.

With its innovative tools and long-term vision, the GreenEURproject aspires to become a benchmark for environmental transparency, helping projects demonstrate their commitment to sustainable goals.

The GreenEUR project is a collaboration between four higher education institutions and one European higher education network: the University of Lorraine (coordinator), Eskişehir Technical University, the University of Vigo, Vytautas Magnus University, and the European University Foundation (EUF).

The context

Over the past few decades, the number of scientific research projects has significant progress. As a matter of fact, the process activities such as local/international meetings, mobilities, usage of venues, etc., during the project life cycle, and their environmental impacts are usually ignored in terms of resource consumption and their indirect emissions, putting resources consumption, climate change. On the other hand, there has been an increasing demand to reduce the environmental impacts of scientific gatherings. To support these initiatives, various guidelines and handbooks have been published to help achieve green meetings. Additionally, the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) also published the ISO 20121 (20249) on sustainable event management, including requirements and guidance. The ISO 20121 standard outlines various methods for evaluating an event's sustainability, with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) being one of them. LCA methodology, standardised under ISO 14040 and 14044 (ISO, 2006a, 2006b), is a comprehensive approach that examines the environmental impacts and aspects related to a product's production, use, and disposal. Evaluating the environmental performance of scientific research projects is a crucial step toward achieving sustainability goals. In this context, LCA approach provides a systematic and quantitative analysis of the environmental impacts associated with research activities. By considering factors such as mobility, physical and online meetings, materials obtaining, communication and dissemination activities throughout the entire life cycle of a project, LCA enables informed decision-making to determine and minimise environmental burdens and enhance sustainability in research practice. In this project, the flowchart of the quantitative analysis followed is presented in the Figure 1.

Figure 1. *The applied flowchart of the quantitative analysis*

Determination of questions related to activities in project life cycle

In the first step of quantitative analysis, the aim is to develop comprehensive questions that will help identify environmental impacts arising from activities at different stages of the project life cycle, covering activities that are included in or potentially part of these projects. During the determination of questions, it has also been taken into consideration that the questions to be asked of the user, as well as the collection of their responses, should be time-efficient. Accordingly, activities that may be included in Erasmus+ KA2 projects have been anticipated and listed. Relevant questions, user responses, and key considerations regarding these activities are examined together in Table 1. In this way, it is intended to identify project-specific activities and obtain measurable data.

Table 1. Proposed questions in quantitative analysis

Block	Question	Unit	General remark
Mobility	How many physical meetings are planned during the project? <i>(Please enter the number of meeting)</i>	Times	For each meeting, a new question will be generated in the sub-section.
Mobility	Meeting (number; for example, one): Where will the physical (Meeting One) held?	City	This question is intended to make an automatic calculation between the meeting location and the city of each partner, in the preliminary question. Proposals to use the E+ distance calculator (in straight line) or Openstreetmap.
Mobility	Meeting one: How many people per partner will be attending?	N. of attendees	This question is intended to determine automatically total distance calculation related to the previous two question.
Mobility	Meeting one: Which type of transportation will attendees use?	Optional: select between flight, train, bus, car.	This question requires a manual response from the user. Although an automatic distance calculation can be generated based on the kilometres between the visitor's location and the meeting location, direct user input is necessary for the number of attendance and duration of meeting. The user can choose the mode of transportation (car, bus, train, or flight) for each institution.
Mobility	Meeting one: What is the proposed duration of meeting?	days	This question is intended to determine the duration of the meeting in days. The user will only be required to enter the meeting duration. In the background, this information will be used to estimate the accommodation per person per night. The

Block	Question	Unit	General remark
			accommodation type will be assumed to be a budget hotel.
Communication /Dissemination	How many promotional items will be prepared during the project?	Optional. Enter the n. of packs	Promotional items are prepared for nearly all meetings in the E+. So, here it has focused on the preparation of special items rather than the classic meeting materials such as badge holders, pendants, or printed papers. Therefore, it is assumed that each person will receive a set of promotional products consisting of a textile bag, ceramic mug, pen, and notepad. The user will only need to provide the number of extra promotional product sets planned for distribution.
Materials	Which non-IT items do you plan to purchase during the project?	N. of item	This question is intended to identify which equipment or research consumables will be purchased during the implementation of the project. In the background, the environmental impact associated with the manufacturing of these items will be considered.
	How many total “working days” will you work on this project for all activities?	N. of days	This question is aimed to calculate impact of number of budget working days during the project implementation. “1 working day” is assumed as 8 hours.
ICT	How many online meetings are planned during the project?	N. of online meeting	This question is designed to determine the environmental impact of each attend based on computer usage and network connectivity. For each number of online meetings will be open new question in sub-section.
ICT	Meeting 1: How many people will be attending?	N. of people	This question is to determine the number of attended people to the online video conference meeting.
ICT	Meetings: How many hours will the meeting last?	hours	This question is to determine the duration of meeting as hours
ICT	Which IT Material do you plan to purchase during the project implementation? <i>Laptop, Desktop without screen, Printer laser color, Printer black/white, Mobile device, tablet, Smartphone, Keyboard, Optical Mouse.</i>	N. of item	This question is intended to identify which appliances and IT equipment will be purchased during the implementation of the project. In the background, the environmental impact associated with the manufacturing of these items will be considered. Each entry will refer to a single product.

LCA modelling of inventory data related to question

In this step, it was aimed to determine the environmental impacts of the activities or processes related to the questions, it is first necessary to develop a life cycle inventory (LCI). The environmental impacts of the processes included in the LCI are calculated based on a functional unit. The functional unit serves as a reference basis for calculating the environmental impacts of different activities and ensuring their comparability. The use of a functional unit enabled normalization and comparability across different activity types. In this context, the questions directed to users have been associated with the relevant activities or processes (see Table 2). All input (raw materials, materials, energy consumption, etc.) and output (emissions to air, water, and soil, and waste management) data related to these activities or processes were modelled in licensed SimaPro 9.6.0 LCA software (<https://simapro.com>) using the Ecoinvent database (v3.10, allocation, cut-off by classification, unit model). The Ecoinvent v3.10 “allocation, cut-off by classification, unit” model applies the allocation approach to distribute environmental burdens among co-products in multi-output processes. In this system, the environmental impacts from previous life stages of recycled or recovered by-products are excluded from the model (cut-off); only burdens arising within the system boundary are considered. The unit model offers disaggregated and transparent datasets that allow for more detailed and traceable analysis (Wernet et al., 2016). Detailed information on the assumptions made and accepted values used is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Inventory modelling of activity/process related to questions in SimaPro 9.6.0

Block	Related to Question	Activity/Process	Functional unit	Matched Ecoinvent dataset
Mobility	Which type of transportation will attendees use? (physical meeting between partners)	Aircraft transportation	1person.km	This activity was modelled based on the data “ Transport, passenger aircraft, unspecified {GLO} transport, passenger aircraft, all distances to generic market for transport, passenger aircraft ”.
		Passenger train transportation	1person.km	This activity was modelled based on the data “ Transport, passenger train {GLO} market for transport, passenger train Cut-off, U ”.
		Bus transportation	1person.km	This activity was modelled based on the data “ market for transport, regular bus GLO ”.
		Private car transportation	1person.km	This activity was modelled based on the data “ market for transport, passenger car, small size, petrol, EURO 5 GLO ”.

Mobility to conference/ Symposium meeting	Which type of dissemination meeting will be organized?	Drop list: Conference, Symposium		This activity was modelled as multi modal transportation to the conference/symposium venue within the Europe.
Mobility to conference/ Symposium meeting	How many people will attend this conference /symposium meeting?	Transportation	rperson.event	<p>Participants included national (both domestic (local and non-local) and international attendees. Local participants are participants coming from within the host city or its surroundings (approximately ≤ 100 km). This threshold value is commonly used in conference literature, and in the study conducted by Skiles et al. (2022), a 100 km distance is considered as the local range.</p> <p>National (non-local) participants: These participants come from within the same country but from locations farther than 100 km (intercity travel).</p> <p>International participants: These are participants who cross national borders to attend the event. In centrally located European cities, international participation is significant; however, within the scope of EU projects, seminars and workshops are generally dominated by local and national participants.</p> <p>In this study, distance thresholds of 50 km for local participants, 300 km for national (non-local) participants, and 1000 km for international participants were adopted. It was assumed that 60% of the event participants are local, 20% are national (non-local), and 20% are international attendees.</p> <p>Local participants were assumed to travel 70% by car, 25% by public transport, and 5% on foot; national (non-local) participants were assumed to travel 40% by train, 40% by car, and 20% by domestic flights; whereas all international participants (100%) were assumed to travel</p>

				by air. The mobility activity was modelled based on the data of Transport, passenger aircraft, unspecified {GLO} transport, passenger aircraft, all distances to generic market for transport, passenger aircraft ”, Transport, passenger train {GLO} market for transport, passenger train Cut-off, U ”, market for transport, regular bus GLO ”, market for transport, passenger car, small size, petrol, EURO 5 GLO ”.
Physical Meeting	<p>How many people per partner will be attending?</p> <p>What is the proposed duration of meeting?</p>	Accommodation in hotel	1 guest. night	The accommodation activity was modelled based on the data “ Building operation, budget hotel {GLO} market for building operation, budget hotel Cut-off, U ”. A one-day meeting will be considered equivalent to two guest-nights.
		Electricity consumption in meeting place (venue)	1 kWh	Electricity generation activity was modelled based on the data “ electricity medium voltage, market group for electricity, medium voltage Europe without Switzerland ”. One day meeting is assumed to be equivalent to 8 hours. The amount energy consumption in venue was modelled using the D'Agostino et al. (2021); Jens Laustsen et al. (2011).
Communication /Dissemination	<p>How many promotional items will be prepared during the project?</p>	Purchasing of one pack for each person	1 pack for each person	The promotional item activity was modelled as a new process due to missing in the database. Textile bag, notepad, ceramic mug, and pen materials were considered into the promotional item and included in the model. Hence, this activity was modelled using the data as textile, nonwoven polyester

				<p>GLO”, notepad “market for graphic paper, 100% recycled GLO; and market for kraft paper RoW”, ceramic mug “market for sanitary ceramics GLO; market for alkyd paint, white, without solvent, in 60% solution state RoW; market group for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified GLO”, and pen “market for polyethylene, low density, granulate GLO”.</p>
Materials	Which non-IT items do you plan to purchase during the project?	electric kettle	iproduct	<p>Non-IT materials was determined to be considered in the analysis, and their modelling was carried out based on data “market for electric kettle GLO”, “market for coffee maker GLO”, “market for refrigerator GLO”, “market for washing machine GLO”, and “market for microwave oven GLO”.</p>
		coffee maker	iproduct	
		refrigerator	iproduct	
		washingmachine	iproduct	
		microwave oven	iproduct	
Materials	How many total “working days” will you work on this project for all activities?	Working day	rworking.day	<p>The working day activity was modelled based on spending energy consumption resulted from the operation of computer and internet access. It was assumed that “1 working day” is 8 hours. This activity was modelled based on the data “operation, computer, laptop, 68% active work GLO” and “market for internet access, work, 0.2 Mbit/s GLO”.</p>
Online Meeting	How many hours will the online meeting last?	Meeting (Video conference)	ihour.person	<p>The online meeting activity was modelled considering operation of computer, and internet access process data. The meeting model was carried out for “1 hour for person”. This meeting was modelled based on the data “internet access, videoconference, 0.7 Mbit/s {GLO}; market for internet access, videoconference, 0.7 Mbit/s, Cut-off, U” and “operation, computer, laptop, 68% active work {GLO}; market for operation,</p>

				computer, laptop, 68% active work, Cut-off, U .
ICT	Which IT material do you plan to purchase during the project implementation?	Laptop	iproduct	The manufacturing of IT materials was only considered in the analysis. The modelling of these products was carried out based on data “market for computer, laptop GLO” , “market for computer, desktop, without screen GLO” , “market for printer, laser, colour GLO” , “market for printer, laser, black/white GLO” , “market for consumer electronics, mobile device, tablet GLO” , “market for consumer electronics, mobile device, smartphone GLO” , “market for television GLO” , “Keyboard {GLO} market for keyboard Cut-off, U” , “Pointing device, optical mouse, with cable {GLO} market for pointing device, optical mouse, with cable Cut-off, U
		Desktop without screen	iproduct	
		Printer laser color	iproduct	
		Printer black/white	iproduct	
		Mobile device, tablet	iproduct	
		Smartphone	iproduct	
		TV	iproduct	
		Keyboard	iproduct	
		Optical Mouse	iproduct	

Life Cycle Impact Assessment Analysis (LCIA): Interpretation and evaluation of results for five quantitative indicators

LCIA helps interpret LCA studies by transforming emissions and resource extractions into a limited set of environmental impact scores. This is carried out thanks to so-called characterisation factors. Characterisation factors demonstrate the environmental impact per unit of stressor (e.g. per kg of resource used or emission released). There are two mainstream ways of deriving characterisation factors: at the midpoint or the endpoint. Characterisation factors at the midpoint level are located somewhere along the impact pathway, typically at the point after which the environmental mechanism is identical for all environmental flows assigned to that impact category. There is a difference in the unit of the indicator for each category and the unit of the midpoint characterisation factor. This is because a reference substance has been introduced, so that the characterisation factor is a dimensionless number that expresses the strength of an amount of a substance relative to that of the reference substance (Huijbregts et al. 2017).

In this work package (WP2.1), following the development of the LCI, the LCIA analysis was conducted to calculate the potential environmental impacts of the activities/processes associated with these questions. This assessment was carried out by modelling LCI data in SimaPro 9.6.0 (considering excluded infrastructure and long-term emissions). The LCIA methodology used was ReCiPe 2016 (H) v1.09 at the midpoint level (<https://pre-sustainability.com/articles/recipe/>), allowing for a consistent evaluation of impact categories such as climate change (global warming

potential: GWP), resource usage (fossil resource scarcity potential: FSRP, and mineral resource scarcity potential: MRSP), water use (water consumption: WCP), ozone depletion (stratospheric ozone depletion potential, SODP), human toxicity potential (risk increase of cancer as human carcinogenic toxicity potential (HTPc), and risk increase of non-cancer disease incidence as human non-carcinogenic toxicity potential (HTPnc) (<https://support.simapro.com/s/article/SimaPro-Methods-manual>).

In this project, five key environmental impact categories, GWP, ODP, Resource Usage, Human Toxicity, and Water Consumption were selected for the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) of Erasmus+ KA2 projects. Particularly these indicators were chosen due to their relevance to the environmental profile of educational, research, and mobility-oriented activities, electronic services usage during the project life cycle. These processes inherently require significant resource utilization (both for fuel and necessary infrastructure), leading to impacts on climate change and air pollution. Consequently, the first four selected indicators are focused on these areas. Water consumption, however, helps as a broader, general indicator applicable across all project activities. In the ReCiPe method, investigated categories and indicators at the midpoint level are presented in Table 3. Through the LCIA analysis, characterization and normalization results were calculated for the functional unit of each activity/process. A data matrix was generated to present the characterisation and normalisation results of these activities/processes across seven different impact categories, as shown in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. However, since the primary objective of this project is to assess environmental impacts based on five selected categories, Table 6 demonstrates the normalised values of these five indicators derived from the data in Table 5.

Table 3. Overview of the investigated midpoint impact categories (CFm) and related impact indicators (Huijbregts et al., 2017)

Impact category	Indicator	Unit	CFm	Abbreviation	Unit
Climate change	Infra-red radiative forcing increase	W.yr/m ²	Global warming potential	GWP	kg CO ₂ to air
Ozone depletion	Ozone decrease	ppt.yr	Ozone depletion potential	ODP	kg CFC-11 to air
Human toxicity: cancer	Risk increase of cancer disease incidence	-	Human toxicity potential	HTPc	kg 1,4-DCB tourban air
Human toxicity: non-cancer	Risk increase of noncancer disease incidence	-	Human toxicity potential	HTPnc	kg 1,4-DCB tourban air
Mineral resource scarcity	Ore grade decrease	kg	Surplus ore potential	SOP	kg Cu
Fossil resource scarcity	Upper heating value	MJ	Fossil fuel potential	FFP	kg oil

ReCiPe 2016 methodology exists in SimaPro 9.6.0 software with characterisation factors at the midpoint or at the endpoint level (<https://support.simapro.com/s/article/SimaPro-Methods-manual>).

Climate change: The characterisation factor of climate change is the global warming potential, based on the IPCC 2021 report. The unit is kg CO₂ equivalents (eqs). This means that GWP represents the most significant global environmental challenge, primarily caused by the emission of greenhouse gases such as CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O. Erasmus+ KA2 projects often involve activities that generate such emissions, including international/local mobility, consumption of energy, and the use of digital infrastructure and products. Assessing the GWP provides a clear picture of the carbon footprint associated with these actions, enabling project planners to identify high-impact stages (e.g., transportation or electricity use).

Ozone depletion: The characterisation factor for ozone layer depletion accounts for the destruction of the stratospheric ozone layer by anthropogenic emissions of ozone-depleting substances. The unit is kg CFC-11 eqs. Although direct emissions from Erasmus+ activities are minimal, upstream processes such as energy production and the manufacturing of equipment used in training, dissemination, or mobility that can contribute indirectly to ozone depletion. Including this indicator ensures that the LCA captures these indirect yet significant atmospheric effects.

Human toxicity and ecotoxicity: The characterisation factor of human toxicity and ecotoxicity accounts for the environmental persistence (fate) and accumulation in the human food chain (exposure), and toxicity (effect) of a chemical. The unit is kg 1,4-dichlorobenzene (1,4-DCB) eqs. emitted. Human toxicity is a critical indicator for understanding the indirect, yet significant health-related burdens associated with project activities. Even though Erasmus+ KA2 projects do not involve industrial production or chemical processes directly, the life cycle of their operations, such as transportation, energy consumption, ICT infrastructure, and material production, can contribute to emissions of substances harmful to human health. These emissions, including heavy metals, particulate matter, and volatile organic compounds, may originate from upstream processes like electricity generation, fuel combustion, or the manufacturing of digital and printed materials. By quantifying the potential health impacts of such pollutants through the human toxicity indicator (expressed as kg 1,4-DCB emitted), the analysis captures both chronic exposure risks and the cumulative toxic load on human populations.

Mineral resource scarcity: The characterisation factor for mineral resource scarcity is the surplus ore potential. The unit is kg Copper (Cu) eqs.

Fossil resource scarcity: The characterisation factor of fossil resource scarcity is the fossil fuel potential, based on the higher heating value. The unit is kg oil eqs. The mineral resource scarcity and fossil fuel scarcity categories will be considered in the **Resource Usage** category, which focuses on the depletion of non-renewable materials and fossil fuels throughout the project's lifecycle. Educational and digital transformation initiatives under Erasmus+ require various material and energy inputs (e.g., electronic devices, printed materials, online services). Evaluating this category allows the project to assess its dependency on natural resources, thus encouraging more efficient use of materials, circular design principles, and sustainable procurement policies in project implementation.

Water use: The factor for water use is the amount of freshwater consumption. The unit is m³ of water consumed. While Erasmus+ KA2 projects are not typically water-intensive, their indirect water use is linked to electricity generation, accommodation, printing, and digital infrastructure,

which can be substantial. Including water consumption ensures that virtual water use (i.e., water embedded in goods and services) is considered, reflecting the broader environmental burden beyond visible operational activities. Assessing this category helps identify opportunities to reduce water demand through sustainable event management, paperless communication, and eco-friendly catering practices. Moreover, water scarcity is an increasingly critical concern in Europe, and evaluating this dimension supports alignment with EU Water Framework Directive objectives and contributes to a holistic sustainability perspective.

Table 4. The data matrix of characterisation results of each activity/process related to the questions

Block	Activity/Process	Functional unit	Impact category						
			GWP (kg CO ₂ eq)	ODP (kg CFC-11 eq)	HTPc (kg 1,4-DCBeq)	HTPnc (kg 1,4-DCBeq)	SOP (kg Cu eq)	FFP (kg oil eq)	WCP (m ³)
Mobility	Aircraft transportation	1person.km	1.1E-01	5.4E-09	4.0E-05	1.6E-02	7.4E-06	3.4E-02	4.1E-05
	Passenger train transportation	1person.km	6.4E-02	2.1E-08	8.9E-05	3.5E-03	9.1E-06	1.6E-02	3.5E-04
	Bus transportation	1person.km	1.0E-01	1.7E-08	3.5E-04	4.5E-03	1.2E-05	3.2E-02	4.8E-05
	Private car transportation	1person.km	2.3E-01	4.4E-08	2.7E-04	2.5E-02	2.5E-05	7.1E-02	1.1E-04
Mobility	Hybrid transportation (to conference)	1person.event	3.6E+01	3.8E-06	2.5E-02	4.7E+00	3.0E-03	1.1E+01	2.2E-02
Physical Meeting	Accommodation in hotel	1guest.night	7.3E+00	5.4E-06	5.4E-02	2.0E+00	5.9E-03	5.5E-01	2.6E-01
	Electricity consumption (in venue)	1kwh	3.2E-01	1.5E-07	8.2E-04	4.3E-02	1.8E-04	8.9E-02	6.2E-03
Com./Dis.	Purchasing of promotional item pack	1pack.person	1.6E+00	3.5E-06	2.2E-03	1.5E-01	4.7E-03	5.7E-01	1.1E+00
Materials (Non-ICT)	Electric kettle	1product	1.6E-01	5.4E-08	3.9E-04	3.1E-02	2.0E-05	4.9E-02	9.0E-05
	Coffee maker	1product	1.2E-01	3.9E-08	2.8E-04	2.1E-02	1.4E-05	3.5E-02	6.3E-05
	Refrigerator	1product	3.7E+00	1.2E-06	8.9E-03	6.8E-01	4.4E-04	1.1E+00	2.0E-03
	Washing machine	1product	4.6E+00	1.5E-06	1.1E-02	8.5E-01	5.5E-04	1.4E+00	2.5E-03
	Microwave oven	1product	6.8E-01	2.3E-07	1.7E-03	1.2E-01	7.7E-05	2.0E-01	3.5E-04
Materials	Working in computer	1working.day	3.4E-01	1.3E-07	1.5E-03	1.0E-01	3.8E-03	8.5E-02	2.6E-03
Meeting	Online meeting (Video conference)	1hour.person	9.9E-02	3.4E-08	2.9E-04	1.7E-02	5.2E-04	2.5E-02	6.6E-04
ICT	Laptop	1product	2.1E-02	1.1E-03	1.1E-01	2.7E-03	2.9E-05	4.3E-02	5.8E-03

	Desktop without screen	iproduct	2.8E-02	1.6E-03	2.6E-01	5.3E-03	6.4E-05	5.8E-02	7.3E-03
	Printer laser color	iproduct	6.3E+01	2.0E-05	1.6E+00	5.6E+01	1.2E+00	1.6E+01	5.0E-01
	Printer black/white	iproduct	6.3E+01	2.0E-05	1.6E+00	5.6E+01	1.2E+00	1.6E+01	5.0E-01
	Mobile device, tablet	iproduct	8.9E+01	3.9E-05	4.0E-01	3.0E+01	5.3E-01	2.2E+01	9.5E-01
	Smartphone	iproduct	3.9E+01	1.7E-05	2.1E-01	1.4E+01	2.4E-01	1.0E+01	4.1E-01
	TV	iproduct	1.9E+00	6.6E-07	4.8E-03	3.4E-01	2.2E-04	5.7E-01	1.0E-03
	Keyboard	iproduct	2.8E+01	1.1E-05	4.9E-01	2.0E+01	8.8E-01	7.4E+00	2.4E-01

Table 5. The data matrix of normalisation results of each activity/process related to the questions

Block	Activity/Process	Functional unit	Impact category							
			GWP	ODP	HTPc	HTPnc	SOP	FFP	WCP	Total
Mobility	Aircraft transportation	iperson.km	1.4E-05	9.1E-08	3.8E-06	5.2E-07	6.2E-11	3.4E-05	1.6E-07	5.3E-05
	Passenger train transportation	iperson.km	8.0E-06	3.5E-07	8.7E-06	1.1E-07	7.6E-11	1.7E-05	1.3E-06	3.5E-05
	Bus transportation	iperson.km	1.3E-05	2.8E-07	3.4E-05	1.4E-07	9.7E-11	3.2E-05	1.8E-07	8.0E-05
	Private car transportation	iperson.km	2.9E-05	7.4E-07	2.6E-05	7.9E-07	2.1E-10	7.2E-05	4.1E-07	1.3E-04
Mobility	Transportation to conference/symp.	iperson.event	4.6E-03	6.3E-05	2.4E-03	1.5E-04	2.5E-08	1.1E-02	8.4E-05	1.8E-02
Physical meeting	Accommodation in hotel	iguest.night	9.1E-04	9.1E-05	5.2E-03	6.4E-05	4.9E-08	5.6E-04	9.8E-04	7.8E-03
	Electricity consumption in venue	ikwh	4.0E-05	2.5E-06	8.0E-05	1.4E-06	1.5E-09	9.1E-05	2.3E-05	2.4E-04
Com./Dis.	Purchasing of promotional item pack	ipack.person	1.9E-04	5.9E-05	2.1E-04	4.6E-06	4.0E-08	5.8E-04	4.0E-03	5.0E-03
Materials (non-ICT)	Electric kettle	iproduct	2.1E-05	9.0E-07	3.8E-05	1.0E-06	1.7E-10	5.0E-05	3.4E-07	1.1E-04
	Coffee maker	iproduct	1.4E-05	6.4E-07	2.7E-05	6.9E-07	1.2E-10	3.5E-05	2.3E-07	7.9E-05
	Refrigerator	iproduct	4.6E-04	2.0E-05	8.7E-04	2.2E-05	3.6E-09	1.1E-03	7.4E-06	2.5E-03
	Washing machine	iproduct	5.7E-04	2.5E-05	1.1E-03	2.7E-05	4.6E-09	1.4E-03	9.3E-06	3.1E-03
	Microwave oven	iproduct	8.5E-05	3.9E-06	1.6E-04	3.8E-06	6.4E-10	2.1E-04	1.3E-06	4.6E-04
Materials	Working in computer	rworking.day	4.3E-05	2.1E-06	1.5E-04	3.3E-06	3.2E-08	8.6E-05	9.8E-06	2.9E-04
Meeting	Online meeting (Video conference)	ihour.person	1.2E-05	5.6E-07	2.8E-05	5.5E-07	4.3E-09	2.5E-05	2.5E-06	6.9E-05
ICT	Laptop	iproduct	2.1E-02	1.1E-03	1.1E-01	2.7E-03	2.9E-05	4.3E-02	5.8E-03	1.9E-01
	Desktop without screen	iproduct	2.8E-02	1.6E-03	2.6E-01	5.3E-03	6.4E-05	5.8E-02	7.3E-03	3.6E-01
	Printer laser color	iproduct	7.9E-03	3.4E-04	1.5E-01	1.8E-03	9.8E-06	1.7E-02	1.9E-03	1.8E-01
	Printer black/white	iproduct	7.9E-03	3.4E-04	1.5E-01	1.8E-03	9.8E-06	1.7E-02	1.9E-03	1.8E-01
	Mobile device, tablet	iproduct	1.1E-02	6.6E-04	3.9E-02	9.7E-04	4.4E-06	2.3E-02	3.6E-03	7.8E-02
	Smartphone	iproduct	4.9E-03	2.9E-04	2.1E-02	4.5E-04	2.0E-06	1.0E-02	1.5E-03	3.8E-02

	TV	iproduct	2.4E-04	1.1E-05	4.6E-04	1.1E-05	1.8E-09	5.8E-04	3.7E-06	1.3E-03
	Keyboard	iproduct	3.5E-03	1.9E-04	4.8E-02	6.5E-04	7.3E-06	7.6E-03	9.0E-04	6.0E-02
	Optical Mouse	iproduct	7.4E-04	4.3E-05	8.3E-03	2.0E-04	1.6E-06	1.5E-03	1.9E-04	1.1E-02

Table 6. The data matrix of normalisation results of the selected five impact categories of each activity/process related to the questions

Block	Activity/Process	Functional unit	Impact category					
			GWP	ODP	Human toxicity ^a	Resource usage ^b	WCP	Total
Mobility	Aircraft transportation	iperson.km	1.4E-05	9.1E-08	4.32E-06	3.40E-05	1.6E-07	5.3E-05
	Passenger train transportation	iperson.km	8.0E-06	3.5E-07	8.81E-06	1.70E-05	1.3E-06	3.5E-05
	Bus transportation	iperson.km	1.3E-05	2.8E-07	3.41E-05	3.20E-05	1.8E-07	8.0E-05
	Private car transportation	iperson.km	2.9E-05	7.4E-07	2.68E-05	7.20E-05	4.1E-07	1.3E-04
Mobility	Transportation to conference/symp.	iperson.event	4.6E-03	6.3E-05	2.59E-03	1.12E-02	8.4E-05	1.8E-02
Physical meeting	Accommodation in hotel	iguest.night	9.1E-04	9.1E-05	5.26E-03	5.60E-04	9.8E-04	7.8E-03
	Electricity consumption in venue	ikwh	4.0E-05	2.5E-06	8.14E-05	9.10E-05	2.3E-05	2.4E-04
Com./Dis.	Purchasing of promotional item pack	ipack.person	1.9E-04	5.9E-05	2.15E-04	5.80E-04	4.0E-03	5.0E-03
Materials (non-ICT)	Electric kettle	iproduct	2.1E-05	9.0E-07	3.90E-05	5.00E-05	3.4E-07	1.1E-04
	Coffee maker	iproduct	1.4E-05	6.4E-07	2.77E-05	3.50E-05	2.3E-07	7.9E-05
	Refrigerator	iproduct	4.6E-04	2.0E-05	8.92E-04	1.10E-03	7.4E-06	2.5E-03
	Washing machine	iproduct	5.7E-04	2.5E-05	1.13E-03	1.40E-03	9.3E-06	3.1E-03
	Microwave oven	iproduct	8.5E-05	3.9E-06	1.64E-04	2.10E-04	1.3E-06	4.6E-04
Materials	Working in computer	irworking.day	4.3E-05	2.1E-06	1.53E-04	8.60E-05	9.8E-06	2.9E-04
Meeting	Online meeting (Video conference)	ihour.person	1.2E-05	5.6E-07	2.86E-05	2.50E-05	2.5E-06	6.9E-05
ICT	Laptop	iproduct	2.1E-02	1.1E-03	1.13E-01	4.30E-02	5.8E-03	1.9E-01
	Desktop without screen	iproduct	2.8E-02	1.6E-03	2.65E-01	5.81E-02	7.3E-03	3.6E-01
	Printer laser color	iproduct	7.9E-03	3.4E-04	1.52E-01	1.70E-02	1.9E-03	1.8E-01
	Printer black/white	iproduct	7.9E-03	3.4E-04	1.52E-01	1.70E-02	1.9E-03	1.8E-01
	Mobile device. tablet	iproduct	1.1E-02	6.6E-04	4.00E-02	2.30E-02	3.6E-03	7.8E-02
	Smartphone	iproduct	4.9E-03	2.9E-04	2.15E-02	1.00E-02	1.5E-03	3.8E-02
	TV	iproduct	2.4E-04	1.1E-05	4.71E-04	5.80E-04	3.7E-06	1.3E-03
	Keyboard	iproduct	3.5E-03	1.9E-04	4.87E-02	7.61E-03	9.0E-04	6.0E-02
Optical Mouse	iproduct	7.4E-04	4.3E-05	8.50E-03	1.50E-03	1.9E-04	1.1E-02	

^aHuman toxicity consists of two impact categories: HTPc and HTPnc. ^bResource usage consists of two impact categories: SOP and FFP.

In this data matrix, obtained characterization results were transformed to the normalization results using the ReCiPe 2016 (H) v1.09 World (2010) in SimaPro 9.6.0. In the ReCiPe 2016 (H) v1.09 midpoint-level impact assessment methodology (Huijbregts et al., 2017). These characterization results were transformed into normalization results using Equation (Eq.) (1) and the normalization values for World 2010 provided in Table 7. Through this transformation, normalization results are obtained as unitless values (as an output); therefore. These results were considered as input for implementation in the web-based calculator. Accordingly, all normalization results for five impact categories provided quantifiable and comparable insights into the relative environmental performance of the activities/processes.

$$NR_i = CR_i \times NF_i \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

NR_i: The normalization result (unitless) of the relevant activity for impact category i.

CR_i: The characterization result of the relevant activity for impact category i (for instance, in kg CO₂ eq for Global Warming Potential - GWP).

NF_i: The normalization factor specified for impact category i in the ReCiPe 2016 (H) v1.09 impact assessment method (for instance, 1.25E-04 kg CO₂ eq⁻¹ for GWP).

Table 7. The reference value of each impact category to transform characterization results to normalization results

Impact category	NF _i values for World 2010
GWP	1.25E-04
ODP	1.67E+01
HTPc	9.71E-02
HTPnc	3.20E-05
SOP	8.33E-06
FFP	1.02E-03
WCP	3.75E-03

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